

Supplementary Figure S1. Diagram of (a, b) eye and (c, d) shell morphology measurements (see methods for full explanations of measurements taken). Image (a) AW, absolute aperture width; WED, whole eye diameter (including eyestalk tissue). Image (b) LD, lens diameter; LV, lens volume (shaded area); ED, absolute eye diameter; RL, absolute rhabdom length (note that measurements of rhabdom length were taken at regular intervals (circles) within central third of eye bulb ($EB^{1/3}$); see methods). Images (c,d) BWW, body whorl width, as shown on (c) strombid *Strombus pugilis* (fusiform shell shape) and (d) xenophorid *Xenophora japonica* (trochiform shell shape). Images (e-h) show fusiform shells of: e, rostellariid *Varicospira cancellata*; f, struthiolariid *Struthiolaria papulosa*; g, aporrhaid *Aporrhais serresiana*; h, seraphsid *Terebellum terebellum*. Photos included are of specimens sequenced in Irwin et al. (2021), taken by: c, e, h, Barbara Buge, MNHN; d, f, Yasunori Kano, AORI; g, Kevin Webb, NHMUK.

